

Polarographic Behaviour of Isatin-3-Oxime

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The electro reduction of isatin-3-oxime at the D.M.E. has been studied in aqueous Britton Robinson buffers. The reduction product is 3-amino oxindole, and a single irreversible wave, which is diffusion controlled, has been observed at pH's < 10. At higher pH's a dip is formed on the wave plateau and two waves are recorded in presence of certain surfactants, which are corresponding to the reductions of the oxime and its anion.

TWO papers have appeared in the literature dealing with the electroreduction of isatin-3-oxime at the D.M.E. Calzolari¹ obtained a single cathodic wave within the pH range 1.95 to 11.38 in 10% isopropyl alcohol which permits the analytical determination of isatin-3-oxime below pH 7.

Cardinali *et al.*² reinvestigated the subject in aqueous Britton-Robinson buffers between pH 2 and pH 13 and a single irreversible wave was observed. At pH values higher than 10, where isatin-3-oxime is present essentially in its anionic form (pK = 8.3), a dip was found on the wave plateau, owing to the desorption of the anions from the electrode, that causes a lowering of the protonic recombination rate of the anion.

It is to be expected that at pH's ≥ 10 , two waves for the reduction of the oxime (conjugate acid) and the anion should be observed. The present investigation aims to clarify this point. The study includes effects of organic solvents viz., methyl, ethyl and isopropyl alcohol and dioxane in addition to some surfactants.

Experimental

Materials :

Isatin-3-oxime was prepared³ in a yield of about 80% by boiling a mixture of 15 g pure isatin (Prolabo), 8 g of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (B.D.H.) and 200 ml of redistilled water. Yellow crystals were obtained which were recrystallised from ethanol (m.p. 200°-201°).

Solutions and solvents :

Britton and Robinson buffer solutions⁴ were used to provide media with stable pH values which were determined using WG PYE model 290 pH-meter. Methyl, ethyl and isopropyl alcohols and dioxane were purified following the methods cited in Vogel⁵.

Triton X-100 (Rohm and Hass. U.S.A.), sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate (Egyptian Detergent Co.), gelatin and dodecylamine perchlorate were used as surface active substance. KCl and HCl used as supporting electrolytes were of A.R. grade reagents.

The solutions were de-oxygenated with purified nitrogen gas. The temperature was controlled at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The polarographic cell was basically the same as that used by Issa *et al.*⁶ Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode.

The characteristics of the capillary were $m = 1.77$ mg.sec.⁻¹, $t = 3.52$ sec.m^{2/3}. $t^{1/6} = 1.803$ mg^{2/3}.sec^{-1/6} measured in 0.1M KCl (open circuit) at a mercury height of 43.5 cm.

An LP 60 polarograph was used at full scale sensitivity of 20 μA and polarisation rate of 200 mV/min. The limiting currents were determined graphically using the average of the recorded trace swings. The half wave potentials were evaluated from the log analysis graphs of the waves.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms of 2.5×10^{-4} M isatin oxime in aqueous universal buffers are shown in Fig. 1. A maximum appears which is eliminated with triton

TABLE I—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS, SLOPE OF LOGARITHMIC ANALYSIS, REDUCTION CURRENT AND SLOPES OF LOG i VS LOG h PLOTS FOR THE POLAROGRAPHIC WAVE OF 2.5×10^{-4} M ISATINE OXIME IN AQUEOUS BRITTON-ROBINSON BUFFER

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ V(S.C.E.)	$\frac{0.061}{\alpha n a}$	$i_l, \mu\text{A}$	log i ~ log h slope
1.96	0.24	0.062	3.6	0.54
2.55	0.27	0.062	3.5	0.50
3.84	0.31	0.066	3.4	0.50
4.40	0.42	0.068	3.4	0.50
5.24	0.52	0.066	3.5	0.50
6.26	0.53	0.066	3.5	0.50
7.36	0.615	0.068	3.5	0.50
8.71	0.655	0.100	3.6	0.50
9.34	0.73	0.125	3.7	0.50

(0.001%). It decreases on increasing the pH of the solution and eventually disappears at pH's ≥ 5 .

Fig 1. Polarograms of 2.5×10^{-4} M Isatin-3-oxime

A dip in current was observed at pH 's ≥ 9 which was eliminated either by gelatin or Triton X-100. The elimination of the dip leads to the appearance of a new wave, its height is less in case of the use of Triton than gelatin (cf. Fig. 1, curve i). The shift in the E_p towards more negative potentials on increasing the pH of the solution indicates that protons share in the electrode reduction mechanism. The total limiting current is pH -independent.

The values of the limiting current, slopes of $\log i$ vs $\log i$ and the slopes of the logarithmic analysis are shown in Table 1. The E_p - pH plots include 3 segments and the value of mH^+/ne indicates that the number of H^+ ions equal the number of electrons. The investigation of Cardinali *et al.*² on isatin oxime indicates that the total number of electrons equals four giving the amine as reduction product⁷.

The two waves observed at pH 's 6-10 in the work of Souhay and Ser⁷ on the reduction of normal oximes were interpreted on the basis that the current of the first wave is limited by the rate of protonation of the oxime to form its conjugate

acid^{7,8}. The 2nd wave on the other hand is due to pH -independent reduction of the oxime. The two waves are not due to the separate reduction of the oxime and anion, since the pK_a of oximes is near 11, the oxime is present only as free oxime at pH 's < 10 . Although Cardinali *et al.*² have determined the pK_a of isatin oxime spectrophotometrically to be 8.3, they could not observe the wave of isatin oxime anion which would be expected as was detected polarographically at pH 's near the pK_a of the oxime—a matter which has been observed with the reduction of mono-oxime of diketones⁷. The use of Triton and gelatin to eliminate the dip leads to the appearance of 2 waves. The 1st is due to the reduction of isatin oxime and the 2nd more negative wave is due to the reduction of the anion. The two waves are irreversible, the 1st one being under diffusion control whereas the second contains a large adsorption component. It should be noted, however, that no surface active agents were used by Cardinali, *et al.*² to study the dip on the single wave obtained by them.

The kinetic data obtained from Koutecky's equation¹² and the values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ calculated by the aid of a relation due to Delahay¹³ are shown in Table 2.

Effect of alcohols and dioxane on the polarographic behaviour of isatin-3-oxime:

The addition of organic solvents has an effect on the polarographic behaviour of depolarizers due to their influence on the pH , viscosity, dielectric constant of the solution and adsorption on the surface of the D.M.E.¹⁰. Cardinali *et al.* observed that isopropyl alcohol caused splitting of the single wave obtained by those authors at pH 9.95. The first

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS OBTAINED FOR THE POLAROGRAPHIC REDUCTION OF ISATIN 3-OXIME IN AQUEOUS BRITTON-ROBINSON BUFFER

pH	<i>ana</i>	<i>D</i> cm ² /sec	<i>K</i> cm/sec	<i>KD</i> ⁻¹	ΔG Kcal/mole
1.96	0.851	1.367×10^{-7}	3.828×10^{-11}	1.033×10^{-8}	89.652
2.55	0.951	1.023×10^{-7}	1.084×10^{-11}	0.338×10^{-8}	92.813
3.84	0.951	0.964×10^{-7}	6.950×10^{-12}	2.237×10^{-9}	93.934
4.40	0.756	0.964×10^{-7}	6.194×10^{-12}	1.994×10^{-9}	94.205
6.26	0.880	1.023×10^{-7}	5.916×10^{-15}	1.845×10^{-12}	111.645
7.36	0.641	1.023×10^{-7}	9.55×10^{-18}	2.979×10^{-10}	98.915
9.34	0.488	1.143×10^{-7}	3.483×10^{-11}	1.027×10^{-8}	89.889
10.79	1st w. 0.661	1.336×10^{-7}	7.228×10^{-12}	1.973×10^{-14}	122.730
	2nd w. 0.630		8.53×10^{-22}	2.328×10^{-19}	151.208
11.15	1st w. 0.710	1.143×10^{-7}	7.345×10^{-17}	2.166×10^{-14}	122.689
	2nd w. 0.686		2.455×10^{-21}	7.24×10^{-19}	148.555

wave was obliterated in the presence of $\geq 20\%$ isopropyl alcohol. The same phenomenon, however, were observed in the presence of tetra-ethyl ammonium or phenyl trimethyl ammonium ions.

Polarograms of $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ isatin oxime were recorded at pH 11.15 in presence of 0.001% Triton X100. When different percentages of methyl, ethyl and isopropyl alcohols and dioxane were added, it was found that the 1st wave height gradually decreases on increasing the percentage of the organic solvent. The first wave was completely vitiated at a certain percentage of the solvent depending on the nature of the organic solvent. These values amount 20% of either methyl or ethyl alcohol, $\sim 10\%$ of isopropyl alcohol and $\sim 24\%$ of dioxane. It is concluded that the reduction of isatin oxime is hindered in the presence of the adsorbed organic solvent and only the wave of the anion was observed in presence of the above mentioned percentage of the organic solvent. Assuming that the equilibrium between isatin oxime and its anion is re-established rapidly at the electrode surface, the total limiting current is not affected in the presence of the organic solvents but decreases slightly due to viscosity changes.

Effect of surface active substances (S.A.S.) :

Three types of S.A.S., viz., neutral (triton X-100), anionic (sodium dodecylbenzene sulphonate Na-DBSO₃) and cation (dodecylamine perchlorate DAP) have been investigated in order to study the effects of their adsorption on the polarographic behaviour of isatin oxime (Britton-Robinson buffer of pH's 2.55 and 11.15 were selected as supporting electrolytes) for DAP precipitates in alkaline pH's.

Behaviour in presence of Triton X-100

It suppresses the acute maximum observed at pH 2.55. On further addition of the SAS, the single

wave observed was shifted to more negative potentials with a decrease in limiting current. At higher pH's the dip observed was eliminated at 0.0015% triton with the appearance of a more negative small wave which may be attributed to an inhibited reduction at the covered surface of the D.M.E.

Behaviour in presence of DAP :

At pH 2.55 the effect is the same as that of triton X-100 as regards E_1 but has no effect on the limiting current.

Effect of NaDBSO₃ :

At pH 2.55 no change in E_1 and i could be observed, only the elimination of the maxima could occur. At the higher pH's, the effect is less than in the case of triton only.

Polarographic behaviour of isatin-3-oxime in unbuffered media :

Several polarograms were recorded for $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ isatin oxime in 0.1M KCl (pH 6.13) as supporting electrolyte containing different concentrations of HCl as shown in Fig. 2.

On addition of the acid a splitting of the observed wave occur. The new wave (the more +ve one) is attributed to the part of the depolarizer which is reduced by uptake of H⁺ ions supplied by HCl while the parent wave includes H⁺ ions supplied by H₂O. The height of the small wave increases till the two waves combine in one wave. Comprehensive studies have been made by Ruetschi and Trumpler¹¹ on the splitting of the principal wave of the reversible reduction of azo benzene in KCl slightly acidified with HCl. It was found that the splitting depends upon the flux of H⁺ ions whether it exceeds that of the depolarizer or does not. However, the same phenomenon could be observed in irreversible electrode processes such

Fig 2. Polarograms of $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ Isatin-3-oxime in 0.1 M KCl mixture

as the case under consideration. In the presence of excess HCl, a new more negative wave $E_1 = -1.58 V$ was observed (cf. Fig. 2 curve, e) which is corresponding to the reduction of H^+ ions.

Effect of concentration of isatin oxime :

The i_l for the reduction of the depolarizer in HCl free KCl was not proportional to the concentration. This may be due to the fact that i_l is controlled by the rate of protonation besides the diffusion. The agreement is well in buffer -40% dioxane medium and $2.5 \times 10^{-4} - 2 \times 10^{-3} M$ can be determined polarographically.

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